

Power Uprates in Nuclear Power Generating Stations

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¹ **Abstract:** Since 1970, the electric utilities have been using power uprates to increase the power output of their nuclear power plants as a cost-effective method of adding generating capacity. The cost of the modifications for power uprates is less than constructing new fossil plants. National Electric Institute (NEI) said that the power uprates were equivalent to adding a large power plant to the electrical grid, at a fraction of the cost of building a new reactor. The President's speech in February 2003, noted that the nation's 103 nuclear power plants are by far the largest electricity source that does not pollute the air. From 1977 to May 2003, the US Nuclear Regulatory Commission (NRC) has approved 101 power uprates, resulting in an increase of approximately 12448 MWt or 4149 MWe. The three types of power uprates are Measurement uncertainty recapture power uprate (up to 2%); Stretch Power Uprate (2- 7%) and Extended Power Uprate (7-20%). For each power uprate, with the production of additional MWe by the generator, there is depletion of MVAR. This means that by Improving the power factor MWe production is increased but the production of MVAR is reduced which is a concern with the power uprates. To compensate for the depletion of MVAR with the power uprates, the licensees can install the capacitor banks; Increase the generator's MVA either by raising the hydrogen pressure or by rewiring the stator winding/upgrading stator cooling system; install advanced excitation control system; install power system stabilizer or control of MVAR by the Independent System Operator /Regional Transmission Organization. This paper discusses the theory, importance of power uprate and methods of achieving it.

Index Terms - power uprates, MVAR, stability, environmental, generator, LOCA.

I. INTRODUCTION

Electricity demand in the United States is growing sharply requiring more generation capacity. Forecasts indicate that the United States will need about 390,000 MW of new generating capacity by 2020. Nuclear power plants generate twenty percent of the electric energy in the United States. Since 1970, the electric utilities have been using power uprates to increase the power output of their nuclear plants as a cost-effective means of adding extra generating capacity. The cost of the modifications for power uprates is less than constructing new fossil plants. National Electric Institute (NEI) said the uprates were equivalent to adding a large power plant to the electrical grid, at a fraction of the cost of building a new reactor. In 2003, the White House unveiled its plan to reduce levels of three pollutants-nitrogen oxides, sulfur dioxide and mercury from power plants. Its proposal would take full effect in 2018.

^{1*} **DISCLAIMER** -- This paper represents the views of the author and does not represent a Nuclear Regulatory Commission (NRC) position on the subject covered in the paper. This paper is not a substitute for regulations, and compliance with it is not required. Methods and solutions different from those set out in the paper could be applied

Tougher regulations are urged on power plant emissions since the pollutants cause premature deaths. The President's speech in February 2003, noted that the nation's 103 nuclear power plants are by far the largest electricity source that does not pollute the air. Power Uprates at existing reactors can add the equivalent of 6,500-8,500 MW in addition to those uprates already approved by the US Nuclear Regulatory Commission (NRC). Reviews of power uprate requests are a high priority and are therefore, being conducted on accelerated schedules. One MW is said to be used by 1,000 American homes.

With some simple improvements in existing equipment, 20 nuclear reactors in six states were able to expand their generating capacity by more than 1,091 megawatts (MW) in 2001. Since May 2003, NRC completed reviews of seven power uprate applications, resulting in a combined increase of 116 MWe. One hundred and one power uprate applications have been approved from 1977 to June 23, 2004, resulting in a combined increase of approximately 12448 MWt or 4149 MWe. NRC is currently reviewing four power uprate applications that could provide an additional 159 MWe to the electric generating capacity. With the power uprates over the next five years, 28 additional power uprate applications are expected which would result in an increase of about 1886 MWe.

II. POWER UPRATES

A. Why Reactive Power is Important?

In the ac power system both voltage and current vary sinusoidally over time with a frequency of 60 Hz. In real power(measured in watts), both current and voltage are in phase with each other. The product of voltage and current in a reactance circuit is called volt ampere reactive (VAR) power. The reactive power is non-productive and does not register on the customer's watt-hour meters. As VAR flow increases, the efficiency of energy delivery decreases. In a capacitive circuit, the current leads the voltage and produces leading VARs and adds algebraically to the circuit's lagging VARs. By compensating the VARs from the circuit load, the circuit can carry more real power (Watts) and improve the power factor. The reactive power resources are provided at regular intervals as it is difficult to push MVAR across distances. Down-line capacitors boost voltage and flatten a voltage profile along feeders.

B. What Happens With The Power Uprates?

For each power uprate, with the production of additional MWe by the generator, there is depletion of MVAR. This is due to the fact that the MVA rating of the generator is fixed represented by the formula $(MVA)^2 = (MW)^2 + (MVAR)^2$. For

example, for 1.5% power uprate, the main generator output can be increased from 699 MWe at 0.896 pf (i.e., 780 MVA) to 734 MWe at 0.941 pf and the production of MVAR is reduced from 372 MVAR to 265 MVAR. The main generator can operate within the range of exporting 265 MVAR (lagging power factor) and importing 100 MVAR (leading power factor). When the generator is overexcited (lagging), it supplies reactive power MVAR to the grid and when the generator is underexcited (leading), it draws MVAR from the grid. The licensees provide grid stability analysis including assumptions, results and conclusion for the power uprate and the compensatory measures taken for the depletion of MVAR on a grid-wide basis. The depletion of MVAR with the power uprates has become an important issue, after the east coast blackout of August 14, 2003 that affected the availability of a stable offsite power system to the nine nuclear power plants.

C. Criteria for Power Uprates

The NRC staff's Acceptance review of the power uprates ensures that the licensee has provided sufficient information for the staff's technical review. The review ensures that the licensee has addressed the regulatory requirements and licensing basis of the plant, and accident analyses submitted to confirm that the plant can operate safely at the higher power level. The transmission system of the nuclear power plant switchyard should be analyzed for a single contingency (loss of nuclear unit, loss of largest generating unit, or loss of the most critical transmission line) to ensure that the grid system remains stable and the plant continues to meet the requirements of General Design Criteria (GDC) 17 of Appendix 'A' to 10 CFR 50 with the power uprates. The power uprates should be incorporated in accordance with 10 CFR 50.90, 50.91, and 50.92. Regulatory Issue Summary (RIS) 2002-03, "Guidance on the Content of Measurement Uncertainty Recapture Power Uprate Applications," dated January 31, 2002, covers analyses of the effect of the power uprate on things such as electrical equipment, major plant systems, and emergency operating procedures for power uprates less than 2%. Review Standard RS-001, "Review Standard for Extended Power Uprates," covers analyses of the effect of power uprates between 7% and 20%.

D. Types of Power Uprates

Power uprates are grouped based on the magnitude of a power increase. The three types of power uprates are Measurement uncertainty recapture power uprates (up to 2%); Stretch Power Uprates (2- 7%) and Extended Power Uprates (7-20%).

1) *Measurement Uncertainty Recapture Power Uprates:* Measurement uncertainty recapture power uprates involve power increases less than 2%. This is achieved by the use of more accurate devices for feedwater flow measurement that reduces uncertainty in feedwater flow measurement and, thereby, provide more accuracy in calculating power. On the generator side, the power output can be increased by improving the power factor. The main generator performance should be bounded by existing design and not impacted by the power uprate.

2) *Stretch Power Uprates:* Stretch Power Uprates are typically from 2% to 7% and usually involve changes to plant instrumentation settings.

3) *Extended Power Uprates:* Extended Power Uprates range from 7% and 20% and may require modifications to major pieces of plant equipment such as the high pressure turbine, condensate pump, heater drain pumps and motors, main generator, and transformers. At one plant, the main generator was rewound and the rating increased from 626 MVA at 0.9 pf to 684 MVA at 0.97 pf. The existing rotor was re-insulated in order to increase the MVAR capability and the generator hydrogen cooling system was modified. At another plant, the generator rating was increased from 1100 MVA to 1265 MVA by implementing the manufacturer's recommendations for hardware modifications including increasing the generator hydrogen system pressure from 60 to 75 psig, replacing the hydrogen coolers and changing the generator stator water cooling system. The rating of the isophase bus duct that connects the main generator to the primary windings of the main transformer and the unit auxiliary transformer was upgraded from 17.9 KA to 19 KA by replacing bus duct coolers. The loading on the main transformer (main generator output minus the house load fed through the unit auxiliary transformers) should be below the main transformer MVA rating. The switchyard breakers should have adequate short circuit momentary and interrupting ratings for the uprate. The unit auxiliary transformers and startup transformers should be able to handle the load increases (condensate pumps, reactor coolant pumps, heater drain pumps etc.) resulting from the power uprate.

E. Evaluation of Electrical Power Systems for Power Uprates

The licensees should evaluate that with the proposed modifications to the systems for the power uprate to meet the following:

1) *Environmental Qualification:* Acceptance criteria for the environmental qualification (EQ) of electrical equipment important to safety that must remain functional during and following design basis events are based on 10 CFR 50.49. This includes changes with the power uprate for loss-of-coolant accident/main steam-line break, temperature and pressure, radiological conditions, and high-energy line break.

2. *Offsite Power System:* Acceptance criteria for the offsite power system are based on GDC 17 of Appendix A to 10CFR50 and Position BTP ICSB-11, "Stability of Offsite Power Systems." The analyses should show that the offsite system stays stable for the loss of the nuclear unit, the largest operating unit on the grid or the loss of the most critical transmission line events to supply acceptable voltages to the Class 1E safety-related buses.

3. *Emergency Diesel Generators:* An acceptance criterion for the emergency diesel generators that supply ac power to the Class 1E buses following a loss of offsite power event is based on GDC 17 for all plant operating and accident conditions.

4. *DC power System*: An acceptance criterion for the dc power system is based on GDC 17 as they relate to the capability of the dc electrical power for functioning of structures, systems, and components important to safety.

5. *Station Blackout*: An acceptance criterion for Station blackout (SBO) is based on 10 CFR 50.63 and involves the loss of offsite ac power and emergency diesel generators with a turbine trip. The staff reviews that the turbine-driven emergency feedwater system, atmospheric dump valves, and dc power are available for reactor core decay heat removal during the coping period.

F. *Compensatory Measures*

The reactive compensation can be supplied from a variety of sources that include system generation, synchronous condensers, station capacitor banks and distribution capacitor banks. For power uprates, the licensees generally modify/replace one or more of the following devices to supply additional MW with the power uprate and compensate the depleted MVAR from the nuclear unit:

- * Install the capacitor banks to compensate for the depletion of MVAR
 - * Increase the generator's MVA rating either by raising the hydrogen pressure from 60 to 75 psig or rewire the stator winding and upgrade stator cooling system. This puts the generator on a better capability curve and can provide additional MW without the depletion of MVAR for the power uprate.
 - * install advanced excitation control system,
 - * Replace main power transformer or change transformer Load Tap Change control.
 - * Upgrade Isophase bus cooling
 - * install a power system stabilizer to provide adequately damping post-transient oscillations.
 - * install Out of Step relay and blocking modifications
- * Control of MVAR by the Independent System Operator (ISO) or Regional Transmission Organization (RTO). If the grid operator needs more MVAR from the nuclear generator, the licensee will produce more MVAR and that means they have to reduce the production of MW to stay within the generator capability curve.

III. CONCLUSION

Since 1970, the electric utilities have been using power uprates to increase the power output of their nuclear power plants as a cost-effective method of adding generating capacity. The cost of the modifications for power uprates is less than constructing new fossil plants. National Electric Institute (NEI) said that the

power uprates were equivalent to adding a large power plant to the electrical grid, at a fraction of the cost of building a new reactor. The President's speech in February 2003, noted that the nation's 103 nuclear power plants are by far the largest electricity source that does not pollute the air. From 1977 to June 23, 2004, the US Nuclear Regulatory Commission (NRC) has approved 101 power uprates, resulting in an increase of approximately 12448 MWt or 4149 MWe. The three types of power uprates are Measurement uncertainty recapture power uprate (up to 2%); Stretch Power Uprate (2- 7%) and Extended Power Uprate (7-20%). For each power uprate, with the production of additional MWe by the generator, there is depletion of MVAR. This means that by Improving the power factor MWe production is increased but the production of MVAR is reduced which is a concern with the power uprates.

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IV. REFERENCES

- [1] Regulatory Issue Summary (RIS) 2002-03, "Guidance on the Content of Measurement Uncertainty Recapture Power Uprate Applications," dated January 31, 2002,
- [2] Review Standard RS-001, "Review Standard for Extended Power Uprates."

V. BIOGRAPHY

Narinder K. Trehan received B.Tech. (Honors) degree in Electrical Engineering from Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, and an M.S. degree in Nuclear Engineering from the University of Maryland. From 1961 to 1979, he worked with different Architect Engineers such as Bechtel Power Corporation, and since 1979, he has been working with the U.S. Nuclear Regulatory Commission.

He has published 26 technical papers at the national and international levels. The chair of "The U. S. President's Council of Year 2000 Conversion," thanked him by a letter for his contribution to minimize the effects of potential problems associated with the Year 2000 date change. He trained Russian and Ukrainian delegates regarding the licensing review of the electrical power systems of nuclear power generating stations. He was a previous member of the Working Group (WG) on IEEE Std. 387. He is currently a member of the WG 4.7 of IEEE Std. 741 and a member of the WG on IEEE Std. 944. He is a Senior Member of IEEE and a registered Professional Engineer in the State of Maryland.